

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Factors influencing fast turnover of teachers: Impact on personnel's satisfaction

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 24(02), 1676–1685

Publication history: Received on 09 October 2024; revised on 15 November 2024; accepted on 18 November 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.24.2.3507>

Abstract

The study examined the factors causing the high turnover of teachers in St. Mary's College of Baliuag, Inc. (SMCB) for the past four school years. School year 2020-2021 was highlighted when twenty-three from the Integrated Basic Education resigned. Records of the said teaching personnel were obtained from the offices of the Principal and Guidance and Testing Center. The data were analyzed using qualitative and descriptive research methods. Exit survey questionnaire and individualized interview were administered in this research. Responses of the teachers were analyzed and categorized into five major factors such as burnout/fatigue, management support, working conditions, interpersonal relationship, and career change. These five factors were given emphasis for resolutions in the formulation of more effective teacher selection and retention policies, enhancement of management support system and faculty mentoring.

Keywords: Fast turnover; Teaching personnel; Private school; Personnel's satisfaction; Management support system

1. Introduction

A teacher is a highly respected person in society and teaching is considered as one of the most revered and distinctive professions. However, there is this problem of fast teacher turnover, a challenging phenomenon that besets school administrators, particularly in private institutions. This is due to the more competitive and higher salary in the public schools. The fact that most private schools are providing better teacher in-service training is downplayed by the more lucrative salary and free education that the government-run schools offer.

The National Foundation for Educational Research (NFER) claimed that teachers can endure greater job-related stress than other professionals. However, this value of long endurance is hard to find among the present generation of teachers which might be the reason why so many of them leave the profession so quickly. School administrators are well aware of this, but they cannot stop it from happening. When confronted with heavy workloads, enormous paper works, and international accreditation demands, it is all too common for even the good teachers to resign. To make things worse, exit of good students follow to show loyalty and sympathy to their teachers.

This research aimed to study the possible reasons for this occurrence in SMCB and its outcome will hopefully guide the administrators to implement better hiring and retention policies, improve management support systems and provide more effective teacher mentoring to minimize the problem.

2. Review of Related Literature

Teachers in general form the democratic ideals, social cohesion, and economic competitiveness of every nation. But despite the central role teachers play in our society, they have long struggled to gain and maintain the status of a prestigious profession. (Kraft & Lyon, 2024) An alarming phenomenon happened during the COVID pandemic where

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there was a growing dissatisfaction, burnout, and turnover among teachers. (Diliberti & Schwartz, 2022; Barnum, 2023) The departure rate of novice teachers is even higher. Research on the fast turnover of teachers has consistently found that the primary reasons for departure are work environments and experiences that are unbearably unpleasant. (Steiner et al., 2022). Annual teacher departure rates in the United States have held steady at about 16% for most of the 21st century leaving serious consequences at both the school and student levels. Moreover, after the pandemic, teachers are reporting levels of burnout and intention to leave the profession at the highest rates in recent history as reported by Marks and Esdal (2023).

Burnout among teachers is not only affecting their lives, but also their students who need adequate attention and guidance. Teachers with high anxiety can impact students as they tend to perform worse academically, particularly in subjects like math, and can develop negative feelings and behaviors. (Peck, 2024). Excessive workload teachers face is the leading cause of burnout. In addition to teaching, many educators spend long hours preparing lesson plans, grading, attending meetings, and organizing extracurricular activities. They even work beyond school hours and on weekends, leading to exhaustion. Statistics reported 23% of teachers considered working excessive hours as a major factor in their burnout. (James, 2024).

Studies have revealed that teachers who demonstrate high levels of organizational motivation, commitment and love for the teaching profession are less likely to leave their jobs. The types of committed teachers can lead to various benefits for schools, such as enhanced stability and continuity in the learning environment. On the other hand, low levels of commitment to the teaching profession might result to a higher number of employees quitting. This may cause great disturbance in the classroom setting and would incur additional expenses caused by recruitment and orientation of new teachers. (QiaLian et al. 2024) Teachers compared with other professions are much more likely to report that they do not feel resilient, and they do not bounce back quickly after stressful or hard times. They have also trouble coping with job-related stress. (Will, 2023) Based on data from the National Centre for Education Statistics (NCES) (Hussar & Bailey, 2020), teachers are quitting their jobs due to overwork, poor working conditions, unfulfilled payment, and lack of sufficient support from administrators, particularly among international teachers. The resignation of teachers from high schools has a detrimental effect on both the academic performance of students and the school's capacity to spend resources for hiring replacements (Tan & Patrick, 2024).

Teachers inspire student achievement. Research finds that high rates of turnover impair student achievement. In schools with a high turnover, inexperienced and underqualified teachers are often employed as replacements. This has a negative impact on student learning. Teachers of mathematics, science, special education, English language development, and foreign languages are more likely to leave their school or the profession than those in other fields. These are teaching fields that experience shortages in USA according to Thomas & Hammond, (2017).

These are a few elements that might affect teacher retention and turnover according to research done by Aulia and Haerani (2023) which are salary and benefits, working conditions, school culture, peer support, teacher-to-teacher collaboration, and individual and family circumstances.

Whether employee compensation influences teachers' turnover, or aspects of career path development, or their level of satisfaction and working conditions, it is imperative for school administrators to pay special attention to these reasons. Teacher turnover is a challenging issue in education that sends alarming message to administrators, teachers, and students. Are there emerging interventions to control the massive migration and exodus of both new and tenured teachers? These intriguing thoughts need concrete answers; thus, this research was conducted because it is critical for administrators to be aware of the factors affecting the fast turnover of teachers so important issues and concerns that target on teacher retention can be effectively addressed.

According to a local survey, teachers consider the quality of their working conditions as important factor in their decision to leave or continue in the teaching profession. Good working conditions include administrative support, availability of professional resources, freedom to express their opinions on matters related to their profession, and the empowerment to influence policy in their schools. Research studies reveal that the teachers who work in affluent and privileged communities experience better working conditions than those who work in low-income communities. Maintaining a steady work force may help reduce the incidents of teacher burnout and attrition. This may inspire the workforce and even motivate the students to experience more effective classroom instruction. Without good mentoring from the seasoned teachers, new teachers can feel lost, tired and frustrated. It is difficult for them to overcome their problems without the guidance of someone who already knows the solution. It is also much easier to keep making the same mistakes without the wise words of an experienced mentor.

The five factors that the researcher identified in the study affecting teacher turnover are burnout and fatigue, management support, working conditions, interpersonal relationship, and career change shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study was to analyze the factors influencing teacher turnover in SMCB. The following questions were addressed:

- What in their job/assignments they considered good, fulfilling, frustrating and difficult?
- What could you have done better for the school had you been given the opportunity?
- What training would you have needed that was not provided to you?
- What made you decide to leave the school?

If there is one important thing that you want the school to improve, what would that be? Why?

3. Methods

This study employed a descriptive survey design and all the teachers who resigned from 2020-2021 were asked to answer the exit survey questionnaire and individualized interview. The questionnaire comprised both structured questions and a few unstructured questions utilizing both quantitative and qualitative techniques in data collection and analysis. The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Lastly, data was presented through frequency distribution tables, graph and pie charts.

3.1. Presentation of Data

Table 1 Profile of Resigned Teachers (4-year period)

School Year	Resigned Teachers	Male	Female
2017-2018	14	4	10
2018-2019	11	2	9
2019-2020	7	0	7
2020-2021	23	7	16
TOTAL	55	13	42

Figure 1a Distribution of Respondents According to Gender

Figure 1 shows the distribution of teachers according to gender, the female is 42 (76.4%) while the male is 13.0 (23.6%)

Table 1 shows that for the past four years, the highest number of turnovers is in SY 2020-2021 with 23 resigned teachers.

Figure 1b Number of Resigned Teachers

Table 2 Causes of Turnover due to Burnout /Fatigue

Responses	Frequency
Enormous paper works required by Accreditation Agencies	49
Stressful Accreditations	21
Burnout/ over fatigue /too many responsibilities	15
Loaded work of teacher	15
Difficulty asking for sick leave/not trusted	9
Exhaustion caused by frequent revisions of Student's Learning Plan	5

Enormous paper works is the top reason why the respondents experienced burnout due to stressful accreditations and loaded work of teachers that led to their decision to resign. Feedback coming from interviews of teachers cited difficulty in being a teacher assistant in kindergarten, work fatigue, increased workload, difficulty in asking for sick leave, lack of autonomy, and student discipline/classroom management problems as cited by teachers who resigned in 2020-2021. One interviewee was asked what drove her to leave; she said that the school being ISO certified has become “test-and-data obsessed”. In addition, to cope with the quality standards of accreditation, the school is acting like a “business model of constantly collecting data” – which is driving teachers crazy.

Since burnout is an alarming and rising problem among educators, it is vital for school leaders to consider what strategies and interventions can be done to prevent burnout and relieve stress for teachers.

Table 3 Causes of Turnover Due to Lack of Management Support

Responses	Frequency
Failed recognition of importance i.e. Teachers' Day, as members of professional organizations	13
Insufficient/Irregular mentoring/coaching for newbies	11
Indecisiveness in decision making	8
Lack of flexibility; Inconsistent/changeable decisions	6
Fear of freely expressing oneself	6
Inability to listen to teachers/ students' requests for fieldtrip, graduation ball etc.) points for comparison to transfer to other schools	6
Lack of consistent presence of higher authority figure	5
Qualification of Officer in-charge/Coordinator, class adviser needs improvement (too demanding)	5
Minimize meetings after exams to finish grades	4
Lack of consistency in words and action for some leaders	4
No provision for parking lot for personnel/parents	4
Misunderstood and branded too vocal	3
Assigned substitute teacher not doing her job	3
Professional gap/ conflict with adviser	3
Not given leadership and moderators' training	3
Favored parents over teachers	2
Unsatisfying classroom evaluation despite hard effort	2
Wanting good leader that treats all personnel fairly	2
Attendance to seminar/training not evenly distributed	2

As shown in Table 3 the causes of teacher dissatisfaction were caused by lack of management support as manifested in failure to recognize teachers' achievements as members of some organizations and special school events, indecisiveness on pressing matters, lack of flexibility and inability to listen.

Burnout and attrition are found both among new and seasoned teachers as well that may be the result of unsatisfied needs. Through the years covered, female teachers reported significantly higher rates of frequent job-related stress and burnout than male teachers -- a consistent pattern since 2021. Female teachers also reported significantly lower base pay than male teachers, but there were no differences in the number of hours worked per week. Within the first few years of entering the field of education, some teachers quit, while others exit only after many years of practice. Teacher unpredictability affects student motivation and enthusiasm for learning.

Table 4 Causes of Turnover Due to Working Conditions

Responses	Frequency
Not given chance to attend seminar outside the school	12
Attendance to seminar/training not well distributed	7
Too demanding parents; harassment	7
Giving one's best but not appreciated	7
Some teachers causing work delays due to late submission of requirements	5
Insufficient mentoring/coaching for newbies	4
Disappointed with colleagues not doing their jobs	4
Frequent changing of calendar of activities	4
Minimize meetings after exams to have time for checking	4
Bullied and rejected	4
Unequal distribution of students (should be 35 only per class)	3
Lack of flexibility on part of some leaders	3
Difficult classroom management (40-45 students per class)	3
Transferring due to personal reason, health, studies	3
Frustrating deadlines for submission of documents	3
Overlapping/conflicting schedules	3
Wanting sincere concerns from superiors and colleagues	2
Difficulty in imposing student discipline	2
Substitute teacher not doing her job	2
Demanding class adviser	2
Not given opportunity to show talent	1
Complaints of parents not listened to	1

As shown in table 4, the top reason that caused turnover due to working conditions is not given the chance to attend seminars outside the school. Others included the following: non-inclusion of membership in the Commission on Higher Education Regional Quality Assessment Team and Council of Hotel and Restaurant Educators as plus factor in the teachers' performance appraisal; not given leadership and moderators' training; need to stop teaching to finish education units; dissatisfaction over ratings received for classroom evaluation despite hard effort; harassment of parents; falling victim of unsolicited jokes/remarks; giving one's best but not appreciated; transferring due to personal reason; wanting sincere concerns from superiors and colleagues; being blamed for helping although not one's job; not given opportunity to show talent and not listened to regarding irrelevant complaints of parents. Parents who are critical

or unsupportive can contribute to teachers' stress and burnout. Constantly dealing with difficult conversations or unrealistic expectations can add to teacher stress, contributing to teacher burnout. (James,2024)

Table 5 Causes of Turnover Due to Interpersonal Relationship

Responses	Frequency
Conflicts among teachers	14
Failed recognition of importance i.e. Teachers' Day	8
Indifferent/unfriendly colleagues	8
Biased opinion of seniors towards newbies (seniority feelings of tenured teachers)	7
Lack of consistency in words and action for some leaders	6
Fear of freely expressing oneself	4
Unprofessional / disrespectful behaviour of some colleagues	4
Unpleasant behaviour of co-workers	4
Varied reasons: Unsatisfying classroom evaluation despite hard effort Some teachers engaged in so much networking; misunderstood and branded when vocal Bullying/rejection	4
Inability to listen	3
Wanting good leader that treats all personnel fairly	3

According to the respondents, conflicts among teachers have the highest frequency, causing turnover. Failed recognition during Teachers' Day, and unfriendly colleagues ranked second. Seniors' attitude towards newbies, misunderstood and branded when vocal, giving one's best but not appreciated, unsatisfying classroom evaluation despite hard effort, some teachers engaged in so much networking and bullying/rejection got the lowest response among respondents.

Table 6 Causes of Turnover due to Change of Career or for Higher Pay

Responses	Frequency
Financial problem	10
Posting overseas- with relative, husband in Abu Dhabi	10
Transferring to public school/DepEd	6
Change of working environment	6
Shift of interest	4
Explore new things aside from teaching	3
Looking for higher salary	3
Sole family breadwinner	2
For greener pasture	2
Full-time housewife	1

According to respondents, financial problems are the main reason that caused turnover due to change of career or higher salary. Pursuing a career in another field of industry, looking for other opportunities outside, applying as factory worker-abroad, being salesman in Dubai, attending office work at Napolcom, being and full-time housewife got the least response from the respondents.

Some studies suggest that salary may not be the priority reason for teachers' leaving the school, although it plays a significant role when they said they were looking for greener pasture abroad. Majority of the teachers leaving for overseas employment specialized on subjects considered in demand like Mathematics, Science and English. These

specialized areas receive more attractive offers for opportunities outside the teaching profession. Salary is a major factor in attrition among young teachers who are just beginning their careers. At the same time, it also acts as a deterrent to the retention of experienced and well-qualified teachers.

4. Findings of the Study

- The kind of preparation teachers have before employment and the kind of administrative support they receive on the job contributes to the reason for shifting to another career.
- Teachers who enter the profession through teaching certification pathways—who have less coursework and student teaching, are more likely to leave their schools and the profession.
- Teachers of Mathematics, Science and English are much more likely to leave their schools or the profession for greater remuneration in public schools and abroad.
- Lack of administrative support like not being listened to or not appreciated influence teacher turnover.
- Strong Filipino ties, loyalty and support inspire married teachers to look for places of work that guarantee higher compensation for financial stability of families.
- Faced with impossible workloads, endless accountability, i.e. accreditation demands, enormous paper works, the good teachers leave the profession.
- Differential salary increases can improve the local teacher labor market and increase both the size and quality of the teacher applicant pool.
- Some causes of burnout for teachers experienced in the school are extreme number of responsibilities above and beyond instruction; lack of adequate administrative support; evaluation of teachers based on standardized testing scores; increasingly difficult student behavior in the classroom; forcing teachers to teach outside of area of expertise; inadequate preparation time due to several meetings and accreditations; extreme amounts of paperwork; a lack of respect for colleagues, teacher against teacher or teacher against superior; lack of adequate staffing and challenging interactions with parents.

Recommendations

- Intensify strategies to improve the retention of teachers by giving fair treatment for all, equal opportunities to attend seminars and trainings for wholistic development, freedom to express oneself without being considered vocal and rebellious, paying them right, offering flexible work schedules, being generous with praise and recognition.
- Provide a comfortable work environment and culture and prepare a career road map to make teaching more manageable and sustainable.
- Consistently implement policies on faculty development, sick leave, study leave, salary incentives and promotions.
- Lessen teachers' stress and workload by organizing an "expert core group" during ISO audits and PAASCU visits to prepare needed documents.
- Organize a professional development program intended for the academic and character formation of all the personnel.
- Appoint qualified coordinators based on both intelligence (IQ) and emotional intelligence (EQ).
- Distribute properly workloads for teachers to avoid overloading or underloading.
- Encourage collaboration among teachers by fostering a culture of teamwork and providing opportunities for professional learning communities (PLCs). Create spaces where teachers can connect and support each other.

5. Conclusion

The massive teacher turnover in the school year 2020-2021 had a significant impact on the financial and human resources of the school. There exist significant financial costs as reported in the financial budget of the school associated with recruiting, hiring, and training new teachers. Teacher turnover is contributing to a big financial loss when in fact the money could be used to fund more effective recruitment and promotion campaign, wholistic staff development program and hiring procedures. It can also provide additional research training and seminars, international exchange program and benchmarking to boost personnel's experience and expertise. In some studies, on the cost of teacher turnover, researchers estimated the financial costs could be as much as 150 percent of the leaving teacher's salary, or an average estimate of 20 percent. Conditions such as poor health and adverse working conditions are associated with intentions to leave their jobs as reported by teachers and principals. Supportive school environments are linked to better well-being and a decreased likelihood of intentions to leave.

Therefore, high rates of teacher turnover may have a significant negative effect on school reputation and climate. It can complicate the ability of schools to plan and implement new programs, conduct professional development, and provide support systems for faculty. Teacher turnover is something that every school should take seriously. Efficient administrators should hire the right teachers. Keeping teachers starts with hiring the right people. The teachers, being human, need encouragement and recognition. When teachers do something right, the administration should show appreciation. When the teachers accomplish a difficult project or submit it before the deadline, they need to be commended. Most teachers want to increase their skills and knowledge and move up the career ladder. Showing them, a projected career path gives them a sense of direction and purpose. Teacher turnover cannot be disregarded but the administration can reduce teacher turnover by providing a favorable working environment for them.

As a conclusion, the study validated the five major reasons why there is fast teacher turnover in the school namely Burnout/Fatigue with the highest frequency rate of responses (F=114); followed by Management Support (F=92); Working Conditions (F=86); Interpersonal Relationships (F=65); and Career change (F=47). With these reasons that came to the fore, the administration should try to formulate strategic plans to respond to the needs of the teachers, thus minimizing the migration of teachers.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] Aulia, N. & Haerani, I. (2023). Teacher Retention and Turnover: Exploring the Factors that Influence Teacher Decision-Making. Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369010523_Teacher_Retention_and_Turnover_Exploring_the_Factors_that_Influence_Teacher_Decision-Making.
- [2] James, S. (2024). The Complete Guide to Teacher Burnout: Causes, Statistics, and Solutions Retrieved from: <https://educationwalkthrough.com/8-causes-of-teacher-burnout/>
- [3] Keppel, M. (2017). Five Ways to Reduce Employee Turnover. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/mikekappel/2017/08/09/5-ways-to-reduce-employee-turnover/#5643f0505001>
- [4] Kraft & Lyon (2024). The Rise and Fall of the Teaching Profession: Prestige, Interest, Preparation, and Satisfaction over the Last Half Century. Retrieved from <https://edworkingpapers.com/sites/default/files/Kraft%20Lyon%20-%20State%20of%20the%20Teaching%20Profession%20-%20April%202024.pdf>
- [5] Marks & Esdal (2023). Understanding Teacher Retention at Teacher-Powered Schools. Retrieved from: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED634122.pdf>
- [6] Peck, D. (2024). Why Teachers Quit in 2024. Retrieved from: <https://www.devlinpeck.com/content/teacher-burnout-statistics>
- [7] Porter, D. & McGuire, S. (2023). Embracing Joy: A Light through the Tunnel of Teacher Burnout. Retrieved from: <https://think.iafor.org/embracing-joy-a-light-through-the-tunnel-of-teacher-burnout/>
- [8] QiaLian et al. (2024), Exploring the Teachers' Organizational Commitment and Turnover in High School. Retrieved from: https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/21871/exploring-the-teachers-organizational-commitment-and-turnover-in-high-school.pdf
- [9] Steiner et al. (2022). Restoring Teacher and Principal Well-Being Is an Essential Step for Rebuilding Schools. Retrieved from: https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA1108-4.html
- [10] Swartzter, K. (2018). The Cause of Teacher Burnout: What Everyone Needs to Know. Retrieved from: <https://www.learnersedge.com/blog/causes-of-teacher-burnout>
- [11] Sy et al. (2024). Teacher Well-Being and Intentions to Leave in 2024. Retrieved from: https://www.rand.org/pubs/research_reports/RRA1108-12.html

- [12] Tan and Patrick (2024). What's the Cost of Teacher Turnover? Retrieved from: <https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/product/2024-whats-cost-teacher-turnover-factsheet>
- [13] Thomas, D. & Hammond, L. (2017). Teacher Turnover: Why it Matters and What We Can Do About It. Retrieved on March 20,2019 from: https://learningpolicyinstitute.org/sites/default/files/productfiles/Teacher_Turnover_Report.pdf
- [14] Will, M. (2023). The Teaching Profession in 2023 (in Charts). Retrieved from: <https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/the-teaching-profession-in-2023-in-charts/2023/12>
- [15] Worth, T. (2019). Teachers experience more stress than other workers, a study shows. <https://www.theguardian.com/education/2019/feb/25/teachers-experience-more-stress-than-other-workers-study-shows>